

How-to guidelines

for the prioritisation of reviews
of research protocols during
global crises: a framework for
research ethics committees

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How-to guidelines for the prioritisation of reviews of research protocols during global crises: a framework for research ethics committees

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Executive Summary

During sudden, global crises, when confronted with limited resources and increasing workloads, research ethics committees (RECs) may want to or need to adjust the order in which they perform ethical reviews of research protocols. **This guidance is designed to support RECs in addressing three key aspects related to the prioritisation of research protocols during global crises, drawing on lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic.**

First, it assists RECs in determining whether existing prioritisation systems require modification and explores the possible implications of such changes. Then, it details the structural and procedural arrangements necessary to implement new systems of prioritisation. Finally, it outlines the criteria RECs should consider if they choose to revise their prioritisation approach.

These guidelines are informed by a **global survey of RECs** conducted between December 2024 and January 2025 as well as existing literature on research prioritisation during the COVID-19 pandemic (Gelinas et al., 2018; Jayaweera et al., 2021; Sisk & DuBois, 2020; Cornell, 2022; WHO, 2025; Meyer et al., 2021; Paleoudis et al., 2021).

To facilitate practical application, **reflection questions are included throughout** the guidelines to help RECs critically assess their prioritisation processes and prepare for future crises. These questions are designed to encourage proactive planning and support RECs in balancing ethical considerations with operational challenges during global emergencies.

3 Parts of How-to Guidance

1. Should my REC decide to change its system for prioritising research during a global crisis?

2. How should prioritisation take place?

3. Which prioritisation criteria should RECs focus on during a global crisis?

Introduction

Research ethics committees (RECs) – also known as institutional review boards (IRBs) and ethics review committees (ERCs) – assess the ethical implications of research. According to the Declaration of Helsinki, their key responsibility is to “protect the life, health, dignity, integrity, autonomy, privacy, and confidentiality” of research participants (WMA, 2024). They also consider the broader impact of research on society and the environment.

Global crises, however, can place **RECs under significant strain**. During crises, RECs may face an increased number of research proposals to review, often alongside limited resources (Seedall & Tambornino, 2023).

Our study indicates that this pressure may prompt adjustments to their prioritisation systems. While changes to prioritisation systems during a crisis may be necessary, we explain that these changes may also introduce ethical and practical challenges.

Considering the fundamental role of RECs in upholding research ethics during crises, we suggest that changes to prioritisation systems are not always required and should be made with caution. When changes are needed, RECs should begin by considering the structural and procedural aspects of their operations. Furthermore, where RECs are involved in setting or applying prioritisation criteria, these should be selected thoughtfully and transparently.

These guidelines provide key reflection questions to assist RECs in making these decisions:

REC Decisions Regarding Prioritisation:

1. Whether to adjust their prioritisation systems during global crises
2. What institutional changes may be needed if adjustments are made
3. Key criteria to consider when prioritising the review of research protocols under a revised system

These guidelines are based on the findings of a survey of 324 global RECs (conducted from December 2024 to January 2025)¹ and an analysis of existing literature on research prioritisation during COVID-19 (Gelinas et al., 2018; Jayaweera et al., 2021; Sisk & DuBois, 2020; Cornell, 2022; WHO, 2025; Meyer et al., 2021; Paleoudis et al., 2021).

¹ Please see the methodology supplement for a description of our study design.

Should my REC change its system for prioritising the review of research protocols during a global crisis?

During a global crisis, RECs must determine whether their existing prioritisation systems can effectively manage possible increases in the number of research proposals. Some RECs may find that their current processes are sufficient, while others may need to adapt their systems due to high workloads and resource constraints. The responsibility of RECs to uphold ethics standards – as enshrined in the Declaration of Helsinki (WMA, 2024) – remains paramount and should not be compromised by the urgency of research.

This section provides questions to help RECs assess whether a change in their prioritisation systems is necessary, identify the factors that should guide this decision, and consider the possible implications of such a change.

Understanding your REC's current prioritisation system

Prioritisation refers to the process of determining the order and importance of tasks or decisions, particularly when resources are limited. In the context of ethics review, prioritisation ensures that research proposals are reviewed in a way that balances the timely generation of knowledge with the protection of participants, society, and the environment.

Prioritisation is about considering what goals research should pursue and designing research structures around these goals (Cornell, 2022). **Every REC engages with prioritisation in some form, whether through formal processes or implicit frameworks.** Some RECs, for example, may review protocols in the order they are received, while others may give preference to research based on its type, discipline, perceived urgency, or other factors. Both approaches are forms of prioritisation.

During global crises, RECs may adjust their prioritisation systems. In our survey, 60% of global RECs reported changing their prioritisation systems during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Changes to REC prioritisation systems during COVID-19

Question to consider:

- What prioritisation system does our REC already use?

Increased workloads

In global crises, the volume of submissions of research protocols to a REC may increase significantly. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many RECs reported **a surge in protocol submissions**, the duplication of some research, and competition for limited participant pools (Gelinas et al., 2018; Meyer et al., 2021). Many of our survey respondents similarly confirmed this, noting they were overwhelmed with requests, with some even sacrificing personal time to conduct reviews.

In our survey, **79% of RECs reported facing major challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic**, including maintaining an appropriate speed of reviews (57%), the attendance and participation of ethics review body members at meetings (36%), the ability to monitor approved research protocols (30%), and the quality of reviews (21%). Moreover, **RECs that reported facing these significant challenges were around three times more likely to modify their prioritisation systems.**²

REC challenges faced during COVID-19

² Chi-squared: $p = 7.59e-05$; Logistic Regression: $p < 0.001$, Odds Ratio = 3.09.

Increased workloads (cont)

REC challenges faced during the pandemic*

*Respondents were asked to select all that applied.

** Other challenges cited in the qualitative results included the following: insufficient secretariat capacity, difficulties in finding available external experts – particularly clinicians on the front lines – a lack of technical support, and inadequate REC training for reviewing crisis-related research.

However, **not all RECs felt the need to change their systems**. Some (28%) did not experience an increase in their workload, while others (28%) managed increased workloads by adapting existing processes, such as streamlining remote work. Yet other RECs (13%) focused on non-pandemic-related research and thus reported few increases in protocols for review.

No significant increase in workload

Existing processes sufficient for managing workload

Existing processes sufficient for managing workload **28%**

Research reviewed not related to the pandemic

Research reviewed not related to the pandemic **13%**

Questions to consider:

- Is my REC likely to review research relevant to a sudden, global crisis?
- Is my REC's workflow equipped to manage an increased workload?

Institutional policies, regulations, and ethical guidelines

RECs often adhere to policies, regulations, and REC-specific ethical guidelines at the institutional, national, regional, or international level when determining how and in what order research protocols should be reviewed during crises. In our survey, 22% of RECs reported that they followed institutional policies when making prioritisation decisions; 26% followed regional, national, or international policies or regulations;³ and 21% followed other ethical guidelines.⁴ Additionally, some RECs (6%) faced regulatory limitations that prevented them from altering their prioritisation systems during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Other respondents noted the absence of clear regulations, prompting them to develop their own guidelines or to adapt flexibly to new national regulations introduced in response to the evolving crisis.

Regulations do not allow for system to be changed

³ These included, for example, regulations issued by national ministries of health, drug regulatory agencies, and COVID-19 national task forces.

⁴ These included the WMA Declaration of Helsinki, clinical and mental health protocols published by the WHO, the WMA declarations of Fortaleza and Taipei, and the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) declarations.

Institutional policies, regulations, and ethical guidelines (cont)

Institutional and regulatory frameworks can influence, and sometimes restrict, the flexibility of prioritisation systems. Thus, RECs should stay informed on all relevant policies and regulations, particularly in the context of a global crisis.

Factors influencing prioritisation decisions

Questions to consider:

- What principles, policies, regulations, and guidelines are our prioritisation systems based on?
- How might changes to our prioritisation system impact adherence to our institutional and regulatory obligations?

⁵ REC members can refer to [TRREE](#) for national regulations of health research involving human participants.

Ethical implications

Prioritisation decisions should always be guided by ethical principles (WHO, 2025). These principles may intersect in complex ways. Justice in research ethics, for example, can involve both ensuring that urgent public health needs are addressed and that research practices remain equitable and inclusive. Prioritising some studies may be necessary to maximise their potential benefit for society, but this can also mean that other important research is delayed or that resources are unevenly distributed. **Ethical standards are a core responsibility of RECs under any circumstances, and this commitment must be reaffirmed when deciding whether to change prioritisation systems during global crises.**

Even as urgency rises, RECs must ensure that decisions regarding research protocols continue to rely on a **robust risk–benefit analysis**. However, during crises, risks to participants may be more uncertain or evolving. For example, new treatments or interventions developed rapidly in response to a pandemic may carry unknown risks. Assessing these risks may require extra scrutiny, and, therefore, time. If urgency is emphasised without adequate attention to ethical review, RECs risk overlooking important concerns – such as whether participants fully understand the risks involved in experimental treatments, or whether certain populations are being asked to bear disproportionate research burdens. Therefore, RECs should apply a heightened ethical lens to prioritisation decisions and carefully weigh the implications of each choice.

In our survey, **70% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that the prioritisation criteria used by their REC during the COVID-19 pandemic advanced research without compromising ethical standards.** While RECs faced the challenge of balancing the urgency of crisis situations with the need to uphold core ethical responsibilities, many respondents believed that they were able to maintain strong ethical standards in practice.

The prioritisation criteria used by my REC during COVID-19 advanced research without compromising ethical standards

Questions to consider:

- What ethical implications might arise from changing our prioritisation system during a global crisis?
- How might changes to our prioritisation system impact adherence to our institutional and regulatory obligations?

How should prioritisation take place?

If a REC determines that its prioritisation system needs to change during a global crisis, it must first consider several factors that influence how such changes can be effectively implemented. The following sections outline important considerations – both structural and procedural – that RECs should address before focusing on prioritisation criteria.

Transparency

The WHO (2025) guidance on the ethics of health research priority setting states that priority-setting decisions should be “transparent, accountable, and inclusive,” made in a “systematic way” to enhance trust in prioritisation systems. Stakeholders in research – such as researchers, research participants, and funders – should be informed of a REC’s plans to prioritise, including details of how the system will operate (Gelinas et al., 2018).

RECs should clearly disclose the procedures they use for prioritising the review of research protocols; this could involve posting clear documentation on the REC’s website or issuing reports on any changes made to the system.

Question to consider:

- How can we ensure that the procedures and criteria for prioritising the review of research protocols are accessible and transparent to all stakeholders?

Collaboration with other stakeholders

RECs alone do not always determine which research proposals are prioritised. Funders, policymakers, or institutional leaders, for example, may establish broader research priorities early in the decision-making process (Gelinas et al., 2018; Meyer et al., 2021; WHO, 2025).

In our survey, 58% of respondents reported that prioritisation decisions were made solely by REC members and/or chairs, with many committees receiving input from additional sources at the regional, national, or institutional level.

This suggests the need for RECs to actively engage with these stakeholders to inform decision-making on prioritisation, e.g., through advisory panels, forums, or regular consultation.

How were prioritisation decisions made?

Sisk and DuBois (2020) warn that “rearguard actions in the face of global emergencies will be insufficient to address the demands on our research infrastructure.” To avoid reactive decision-making during crises, RECs should initiate collaboration in advance, rather than waiting until an emergency unfolds. Some proactive steps may include conducting joint scenario planning exercises and strengthening forums for communication.

However, **RECs must also remain vigilant of external influences during crises to avoid compromising ethical standards** (Sisk & DuBois, 2020). For example, a WHO pre-workshop to the Global Summit of National Ethics Committees pointed out that RECs often face intense political pressure to fast-track reviews of high-risk, complex studies (WHO, 2023). Similarly, our respondents noted feeling a “push” from governments and institutions to prioritise certain studies, stressing the importance of maintaining independence, where possible, from outside pressures as well as setting clear boundaries.

To help manage political or public pressure, RECs may designate one of their existing members – such as the chair or a rotating representative – to serve as a spokesperson during times of crisis. Even more effectively, where possible, a national REC network could designate a representative to speak on behalf of all member committees. This person would be responsible for communicating consistent messages externally, based on positions agreed upon by the committee or network. Additionally, RECs could require that all prioritisation requests from external actors be submitted in writing and discussed in formally minuted meetings.

Questions to consider:

- Which stakeholders are particularly relevant to the decision to change our prioritisation system during a global crisis?
- How can we effectively engage other stakeholders in discussions about revising our prioritisation system, including in “normal times”?
- What mechanisms can we put in place to manage political or public pressure regarding prioritisation decisions?

Coordination and centralisation in decision-making

Some RECs addressed the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic by **establishing specialised committees dedicated to reviewing research proposals**. These committees varied in focus, with some exclusively evaluating COVID-19-related studies and others concentrating solely on assessing scientific merit and methodological robustness (Jayaweera et al., 2021; Paleoudis et al., 2021; Sisk & DuBois, 2020).

Though the long-term impact of these “COVID-19 research prioritisation committees” remains under investigation (Meyer et al., 2021), some reported that these committees helped optimise resource use within RECs, enabling REC members to focus on broader research disciplines and more deeply on the ethical dimensions of proposed studies, respectively (Jayaweera et al., 2021; Paleoudis et al., 2021; Sisk & DuBois, 2020). In line with this, our respondents highlighted the need for increased coordination between committees, especially at the national level. Several participants also noted that specialised committees, such as those focused on screening research quality, could contribute to making RECs more efficient in managing their workload.

Question to consider:

- Could the establishment of a specialised committee, such as one focused on assessing crisis-relevant protocols or one focused on scientific merit, help streamline our review process during a crisis?

Institutional support for changing prioritisation systems

Our survey found that **many RECs are under-resourced in normal times, with only around one-third of RECs (34%) stating that their funding is adequate**. In addition, 89% of RECs noted that additional monetary resources were not made available to them during the COVID-19 pandemic despite the significant increase in workload. However, changing a research prioritisation system during a global crisis may require additional institutional resources, for example, when establishing specialised crisis review committees.

Perception of funding adequacy among RECs

Institutional support for changing prioritisation systems (cont)

Many RECs indicated that if more resources were allocated to them, their existing prioritisation systems could function without significant changes. Several respondents highlighted that adequate funding and staffing could support their current systems, suggesting that **additional resources might be a more viable solution than overhauling prioritisation systems entirely**.

RECs should consider whether their institutions can provide the necessary backing to adapt their prioritisation systems in response to the demands of the crisis, or if available additional resources would make a change to the system unnecessary. If additional resources are required, RECs may need to advocate for more support.⁶

Question to consider:

- Can our institution provide the necessary resources to avoid changing the prioritisation system?

⁶ See “Strengthening research ethics committees in crises: Why funding matters”, which outlines key statistics, justifications, and potential benefits of increasing institutional support for RECs.

Layering and ranking criteria

When adapting prioritisation systems during a global crisis, RECs must carefully consider not only which criteria to use but also how to structure and apply them in decision-making (Gelinis et al., 2018).

Choosing the right criteria is important (see Section 3), but RECs must also decide which criteria should be applied first. For example, Meyer et al. (2021) outline a three-step approach to prioritisation. In this framework, research proposals first undergo an initial evaluation to meet basic eligibility criteria. If they pass, the second stage assesses whether the institution has the necessary capacity to support all the studies. If the institution's capacity is constrained, the final stage involves comparing studies based on two sets of additional criteria: one tailored to the specifics of each study and the other aimed at enhancing the diversity of the institution's research portfolio.

RECs may also consider using a system to assign weights to criteria during prioritisation. This could involve applying a structured scoring system where each criterion is rated based on its relative importance (Paleoudis et al., 2021). In the qualitative results, our respondents echoed this approach, calling for a grading scale to help ethics committees more effectively prioritise research during high-pressure situations.

Questions to consider:

- In what order should prioritisation criteria be applied?
- Can a scoring or weighting system be implemented to reflect the relative importance of each criterion?

Which prioritisation criteria should RECs focus on during a global crisis?

Assessing criteria for prioritisation during crises

Below, we outline key criteria that RECs may consider if they adjust their prioritisation systems in crisis settings. These criteria are presented as distinct categories to align with the structure of our study, which examined individual factors from existing literature and allowed RECs to highlight additional considerations they found important. However, in practice, these criteria often overlap and interact and should not be considered in isolation.

Relevance to the crisis

During the COVID-19 pandemic, 94% of RECs that adjusted their prioritisation systems reported that relevance to the pandemic (e.g., studies on vaccines, treatments, or diagnostics) was a key criterion.

Relevance to the pandemic as prioritisation criterion

Relevance to crises is a fundamental consideration in research prioritisation, as it reflects the potential of a study to generate knowledge and contribute meaningfully to public health efforts (WHO, 2025). However, determining relevance can be complex, as the significance of research may shift over time, and the available evidence supporting its social value may be limited (Gelinas et al., 2018). Our respondents highlighted that during the COVID-19 pandemic, relevance was defined not only by the focus on healthcare, treatments, and the origins of the pandemic but also by considerations of preventative actions, the broader effects of the pandemic, and social impacts such as restrictions on freedom and movement.

To strengthen decision-making, **RECs should establish clear approaches for assessing crisis relevance**, considering factors such as timeliness, the specificity of the research question, and alignment with societal needs.

Questions to consider:

- How do we define and measure the relevance of a research proposal in the context of a crisis?
- How can we account for evolving crisis conditions that may affect the significance of a study over time?

Diversity

A diverse research portfolio enhances social value by addressing a wide range of scientific questions. A lack of diversity in research can create risks for citizens and participants and diminish overall benefits, particularly if multiple studies rely on the same participant pools (Meyer et al., 2021): for example, participants can be overburdened, or findings may be less generalisable.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, some non-COVID-19 research was paused (Cornell, 2022), narrowing the focus of ongoing studies and potentially overlooking other urgent and societally relevant issues. Our qualitative results echoed this concern, with some respondents noting the suspension of other research during the pandemic. They noted the need to **balance the prioritisation of pandemic-related studies with the continuation of research on other critical issues, such as broader health and social challenges**. Therefore, depending on its scope, a REC should consider supporting studies across a range of disciplines, topics, and methodologies.

Question to consider:

- Does the research portfolio cover a diverse range of research questions and topics?

Responsible inclusion

Equity is a core component of social value (WHO, 2025), particularly in crises, where vulnerable populations may be disproportionately impacted. Research should aim to address the needs of those in vulnerable situations (Jayaweera et al., 2021), which - during the COVID-19 pandemic - included pregnant women, children, minorities, and indigenous populations (Paleoudis et al., 2021; Meyer et al., 2021).

Our qualitative results highlighted that the **needs of people in vulnerable situations** were central to respondents' prioritisation decisions. Some noted that research should be guided by the specific needs of local populations, reflecting the importance of context when determining who benefits from research and how to best meet those needs.

Where special protections are in place, including diverse groups in research can help reduce inequities and prevent the perpetuation of existing vulnerabilities (WMA, 2024). To ensure broad and equitable participation, the Good Clinical Trials Collaborative (2022) guidelines emphasise that inclusion criteria should be designed to allow participation from a wide range of individuals, avoiding unnecessary restrictions that could exclude populations in vulnerable situations.

Questions to consider:

- Does the research portfolio address the needs of populations disproportionately affected by a crisis?
- Do a study's inclusion criteria promote broad and equitable participation with necessary protections but without unnecessary restrictions?

Scientific robustness and study design

In our survey, only 27% of respondents cited scientific robustness and study design (e.g., the likelihood of research success) as a key prioritisation criterion used during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Scientific robustness and study design as prioritisation criteria

Research actors have raised concerns about the quality of research proposals submitted during crises, noting issues such as unclear research questions, a lack of coherent methodology (Paleoudis et al., 2021), and designs that contradicted the current state of the art, rendering studies unlikely to succeed (Meyer et al., 2021). For instance, many clinical trials during the COVID-19 pandemic were underpowered or overly complex, leading to unreliable results or high participant dropout rates (Law & Smith, 2024). **Respondents in our survey also expressed concerns about the scientific quality of proposals submitted during the pandemic.**

For clinical trials, RECs may draw on guidance such as the Good Clinical Trials Collaborative (GCTC) guidelines, which provide detailed criteria for assessing quality, introducing, for example, the following questions:

Questions to consider:

- Does the study address a meaningful research question, and is it accessible to the relevant population?
- Are the hypotheses and expected outcomes clearly articulated in the proposal?
- Does the research design align with the study's objectives and the current state of scientific knowledge?
- Is the proposed sample size sufficient to produce reliable and statistically significant results?
- Are the data collection and analysis methods appropriate to the study's aims and proportionate to the risks involved?

Some RECs may lack the expertise or mandate to assess quality and robustness in detail. However, it is important for committees to discuss and define the specific quality aspects they can evaluate within these limitations.

Feasibility & institutional capacity

Feasibility considerations should include not only the likelihood of achieving enrolment targets and answering the research question (Meyer et al., 2021) but also whether conducting the research is realistic under crisis conditions. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, many institutions faced staff shortages, disrupted supply chains, and limited access to participants, all of which could affect the viability of proposed studies.

Assessing the feasibility of proposed research is particularly important during global crises, when institutional resources are often constrained. In our survey, 27% of RECs reported using feasibility as a key criterion to prioritise research projects during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, RECs who prioritised feasibility were more likely to state that their criteria advanced research without compromising ethical standards compared to those who did.⁷

Feasibility & institutional capacity as prioritisation criteria

The WHO (2025) advises that **cost considerations are an integral part of feasibility assessments**, especially when scarce resources must be allocated efficiently. While most RECs do not make direct funding decisions, their assessments can nevertheless have important resource implications – for example, where delays or refusals may affect the viability or financing of a study. RECs should be mindful of ensuring that limited resources are directed toward studies with the greatest potential impact while avoiding unnecessary duplication of efforts.

Additionally, where RECs have a role in allocating resources or coordinating research activity, they must consider whether their institutions can simultaneously support multiple studies without overburdening staff or compromising the quality of research oversight. The Good Clinical Trials Collaborative (2022), for example, highlights that clinical trials should be tailored to available infrastructure, **making optimal use of existing resources and avoiding waste**. This involves assessing whether studies are proportionate in their use of time, materials, and administrative capacity, and ensuring that trials are not wasteful of staff and participant time, supplies, or environmental resources.

Question to consider:

- Does the institution have adequate staffing and resources to support the study adequately while maintaining ethical standards?

⁷ T-test: $p = 0.028$, did not prioritise feasibility Mean = 3.93, prioritised feasibility Mean = 4.23; 95% CI: -0.568 to -0.033.

Conclusion

RECs may face increased strain during global crises. Yet their core responsibility – upholding ethical standards in research – remains unchanged. **Decisions about prioritising research protocols for ethics review should therefore be approached with caution and deliberate reflection.**

This guidance offers RECs a set of reflection questions to support decision-making around the prioritisation of protocol reviews during crises. These questions are designed to help RECs do the following:

- assess whether changes to their processes are needed,
- identify the structural adjustments required to implement such changes, and
- consider key criteria for prioritising research protocols for ethics review.

In doing so, RECs can navigate urgent demands without compromising ethical standards.

Reflection questions

Should my REC change its system for prioritisation?

Understanding your REC's current prioritisation system

Question to consider:

- What prioritisation system does our REC already use?

Increased workloads

Questions to consider:

- Is my REC likely to review research relevant to a sudden, global crisis?
- Is my REC's workflow equipped to manage an increased workload?

Institutional policies, regulations, and ethical guidelines

Questions to consider:

- What principles, policies, regulations, and guidelines are our prioritisation systems based on?
- How might changes to our prioritisation system impact adherence to our institutional and regulatory obligations?

Ethical implications

Questions to consider:

- What ethical implications might arise from changing our prioritisation system during a global crisis?
- How will we ensure that core ethical principles remain central when making prioritisation decisions?

Structural and procedural adjustments for prioritisation system changes

Transparency

Question to consider:

- How can we ensure that the procedures and criteria for prioritising the review of research protocols are accessible and transparent to all stakeholders?

Collaboration with other stakeholders

Questions to consider:

- Which stakeholders are particularly relevant to the decision to change our prioritisation system during a global crisis?
- How can we effectively engage other stakeholders in discussions about revising our prioritisation system, including in “normal times”?
- What mechanisms can we put in place to manage political or public pressure regarding prioritisation decisions?

Coordination and centralisation in decision-making

Question to consider:

- Could the establishment of a specialised committee, such as one focused on assessing crisis-relevant protocols or one focused on scientific merit, help streamline our review process during a crisis?

Institutional support for changing prioritisation systems

Questions to consider:

- Can our institution provide the necessary resources to avoid changing the prioritisation system?

Layering and ranking criteria

Questions to consider:

- In what order should prioritisation criteria be applied?
- Can a scoring or weighting system be implemented to reflect the relative importance of each criterion?

Criteria for prioritisation in crises

Relevance to the crisis

Questions to consider:

- How do we define and measure the relevance of a research proposal in the context of a crisis?
- How can we account for evolving crisis conditions that may affect the significance of a study over time?

Diversity

Question to consider:

- Does the research portfolio cover a diverse range of research questions and topics?

Responsible inclusion

Questions to consider:

- Does the research portfolio address the needs of populations disproportionately affected by a crisis
- Do a study's inclusion criteria promote broad and equitable participation with necessary protections but without unnecessary restrictions?

Criteria for prioritisation in crises (cont)

Scientific robustness and study design

Questions to consider:

- Does the study address a meaningful research question, and is it accessible to the relevant population?
- Are the hypotheses and expected outcomes clearly articulated in the proposal?
- Does the research design align with the study's objectives and the current state of scientific knowledge?
- Is the proposed sample size sufficient to produce reliable and statistically significant results?
- Are the data collection and analysis methods appropriate to the study's aims and proportionate to the risks involved?

Feasibility & institutional capacity

Questions to consider:

- In what order should prioritisation criteria be applied?
- Can a scoring or weighting system be implemented to reflect the relative importance of each criterion?

References

- Cornell, M.** (2022). (rep.). The justice of pandemic biomedical research priorities: Ethical Framework. UK Pandemic Ethics Accelerator. Retrieved from <https://research-information.bris.ac.uk/en/publications/the-justice-of-pandemic-biomedical-research-priorities-ethical-fr>.
- Gelinas, L., Lynch, H. F., Bierer, B. E., & Cohen, I. G.** (2017). When clinical trials compete: Prioritising study recruitment. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 43(12), 803–809. <https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2016-103680>
- Good Clinical Trials Collaborative.** (2022). Guidance for Good Randomized Clinical Trials. <https://www.goodtrials.org/the-guidance/guidance-overview/>
- Jayaweera, D., Flume, P. A., Singer, N. G., Cohen, M. S., Lachiewicz, A. M., Cameron, A., Kumar, N., Thompson, J., Cabrera, A., Daudelin, D., Shaker, R., & Bauer, P. R.** (2021). Prioritizing studies of covid-19 and lessons learned. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1017/cts.2021.784>
- Law, E., & Smith, I.** (2024). Ethical and informative trials: How the COVID-19 experience can help to improve clinical trial design. *Research Ethics*, 20(4), 764–779. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17470161241261768>
- Meyer, M. N., Gelinas, L., Bierer, B. E., Hull, S. C., Joffe, S., Magnus, D., Mohapatra, S., Sharp, R. R., Spector-Bagdady, K., Sugarman, J., Wilfond, B. S., & Lynch, H. F.** (2021). An ethics framework for consolidating and prioritizing COVID-19 clinical trials. *Clinical Trials*, 18(2), 226–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1740774520988669>
- Paleoudis, E. G., Jacobs, L. G., Friedman, T., Fittizzi, C., Sawczuk, I., & Aschner, J.** (2021). Implementing a review process to facilitate and prioritize COVID-19 research: Staying One step ahead of the pandemic. *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 16(3), 188–192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15562646211017042>
- Seedall, C., & Tambornino, L.** (2023). (rep.). Stakeholder Needs. PREPARED project.
- Sisk, B. A., & DuBois, J.** (2020). Research ethics during a pandemic: A call for normative and empirical analysis. *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 20(7), 82–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2020.1779868>
- World Health Organization.** (2023). Facilitating research ethics review during outbreaks: taking stock, Lisbon, Portugal, 14 September 2022: WHO pre-workshop to the Global Summit of National Ethics Committees. World Health Organization.
- WHO.** (2025). Guidance on the ethics of health research priority setting. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240110953>
- WMA.** (2024). The World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human participants. <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki/>

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